

Possibilities of Shaping the Streets and Squares of the City of Jizsa

Yesbergenov Begzod Yerjanovich¹

¹ Assistant at the Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, Jizzakh, Uzbekistan

Abstract:

In this article, the priorities of the development of the city of Jizzakh, the creation of amenities in the formation of the streets and squares of the city of Jizzakh, the development, renovation and construction of new streets that connect the areas that create the possibility of providing services to the population are put forward.

Keywords: City, street, square, road, highway, industry, square, community, population, construction, new, area.

The planning structure of the construction of the urban environment is influenced by various factors related to natural conditions, land, the existing transport network, planning restrictions, residential construction of the city and neighboring villages, and the location of industrial and communal warehouses. showed.

The existence of the river bed plays a special role in this structure. The planning decision of these parts also includes transport and water infrastructure systems (railways, highways and city streets) that cross the city in meridional and latitudinal directions, as well as throughout the history of the city's development. A number of important factors, such as the formed planning structure, as a residence, etc., were affected.

All this influenced the new planning structure of the residential areas and the main street network, which in turn was determined by the general development of Jizzakh towards the center with outward development routes.

The establishment of the Northern Ring Road will allow transit from the next national highway to Forish District to bypass the city and improve service to the adjacent population.

A regulated network of urban streets was decided to exit the downtown area in each outward direction, connecting residences with places of work and recreation. Given the planning status of the city and its surroundings, the new main street network system is mixed, ie. developed meridional-latitude.

The new and reconstructed highways of the city are being built taking into account the availability of existing irrigation and drainage networks, power lines, bridges and existing roads, as well as norms and regulations for planning, housing estates and urban districts. .

The location of the city center, sub-center and their influence zones is of particular importance in the city layout.

The city's external transport facilities are also kept in their own territory. Railroad facilities, rights-of-way, and the accompanying sanitary buffer zone complicate and divide the urban area. It is planned to create everything from them against 5-10 rows of forest plantations during the passage of the railway. When creating new urban highways and transferring them to the western, southern and eastern parts of the city, it is necessary to build railway crossings, as well as to create bridge structures that cross the river.

In addition, it is necessary to build road junctions of different levels at the intersections of the main highways of the city, which are connected with external routes, connected with roundabouts. Motor transport facilities (bus station, bus station, road service) are further developed in accordance with the calculations made in the master plan to provide these types of services to the population.

The city highway system develops and organizes the existing main street network of the city. This allows to build new residential areas in the city and integrate them into a whole.

For this purpose, it is proposed to create the latitudinal and meridional highways connected to the existing highways of the city, and then to take them to the roundabouts and pass to external communications in the direction of the cities of Pakhtakor, Samarkand, Gallaorol. The establishment of the Uchtepa, New Village Northern Bypass will allow transit from the next national highway to Farish region to bypass the city and improve service to the adjacent population.

A regulated network of urban streets was decided to exit the downtown area in each outward direction, connecting residences with places of work and recreation. Given the planning status of the city and its surroundings, the new main street network system is mixed meridional-latitudes.

Street network - During the 1st stage of construction, the planning project proposes to implement a partial reconstruction and a new construction of the main street network of the city.

The reconstruction of intersections of highways and the construction of canals, roads and railways with them is mainly carried out within the existing limits of the city.

Reconstruction consists in the possibility of creating corridors and corridors of a modern size without separating buildings from red lines. Major reconstruction of the trunk network will affect existing residences. It will significantly improve traffic connections on Sh.

The new construction of the streets will take over some of the traffic along the Sayilgoh Mulkanlik industrial street, which is a continuation of the existing street in the southern region.

The size is set to 50.0 m, the width of the carriageway is 2x11.25 m, to ensure that the central and northern residential areas of the eastern industrial zone are fully connected with the meridional direction of the city highway.

Project highways of regional importance, built on the basis of sections of residential streets, should be rehabilitated to bring the size to 34.0 m and the carriageway to 1.5 m.

During this period, the length of the main streets of the city is 121.4 km, the area is 490.0 ha, the density of road networks is m2.0 km / km2.

The length of the streets to be restored is 58.1 km, and 19.5 km - the network of new streets will have to be built.

The estimated cost of restoration was 58.1 million soums.

The construction cost of the project includes the reconstruction of two bridge crossings over the river.

Cultural service institutions

The construction of cultural and household service institutions of daily importance is accepted in accordance with current standards; for periodic service institutions - classified as follows based on the actual capabilities of the city.

First, the city plans to build daily and periodic maintenance facilities. In the conditions of the market economy, shops, household appliances, bathrooms, and hotels have mostly become private property. They are developing at a fast pace, but their new construction volume is being accepted as per the norms.

The construction of schools, kindergartens, kindergartens, neighborhoods, cultural recreation centers, shops, catering establishments and other service facilities will be carried out primarily on new construction sites.

Measures will be taken to improve utility services in the areas of existing buildings, especially along city highways. In the master plan, the system of providing cultural and household services to the population was developed taking into account the principle of daily and periodic division of services.

Daily service ensures the implementation of services with minimal time costs. This is provided by placing the objects on the corridors with a radius of 400-500 meters and shopping, public catering, public services, near public transport stations.

Time-to-time service refers to the provision of services to suit different needs and individual tastes. It is available in a wide range of specialized stores, cafes, bars, fashion houses, beauty salons, etc., as well as in cultural recreation and other entertainment establishments.

Divided into two categories by this division, the choice of accommodation and services is usually summarized as follows:

- Daily service is provided by creating centers that evenly cover the entire residential area of the city within a radius of 400-600 m. These types of facilities include commercial establishments, public catering, preschools, schools and a number of other facilities.
- Periodic maintenance includes the creation of city centers and residential centers. In the center of the city, there are city-wide service institutions (cultural, commercial, quick service enterprises) that serve not only the residents of the city, but also the surrounding residents, since the city is the center of the system of local settlements. Calculation of service facilities was carried out in accordance with ShNK 2.07.01.-03 "Development and development of urban and rural settlement areas" Tashkent 2003. The number of places per 1,000 people in pre-school educational institutions, secondary schools and non-school institutions is taken according to the age structure of the population.

City passenger transport - In the past, as now, passengers were transported in the city by public (bus, minibuses, taxis) departmental and individual transport. According to estimates, 317 buses of various sizes should participate in public transport during this period. Today, 895 moving parts are working in the city.

The calculation of the required passenger vehicles was done according to the current norms, of which the city should have at least 1020 departmental units, 15640 individual and 340 passenger taxis.

the cost of construction of public parking spaces is 69.70 billion soums.

During the 1st phase of construction, maintenance of the gas stations will be carried out by the gas stations operating in the city today.

In the period under review, maintenance (repair, maintenance, etc.) of 17,000 vehicles, in accordance with the relevant SNK standards, should have service points in the city that can accommodate 91 posts. Currently, there are 3 service stations in the city for 24 points.

In the 1st phase of the construction, it is necessary to build a service station in the car wash complex for an additional 67 posts. The value of these facilities is 4.02 billion soums.

REFERENCE

1. Professor O'Nosirovning "Jizzaxdan aytar so'zim" kitobidan olindi (T., "Extremum Press", 2011y.)
2. O'rol Nosirov va Raya Nurqulova "Jizzax viloyati" O'zME. Birinchijild. Toshkent, 2000-yil
3. O'zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi
4. Yerjanovich Y. B. History of Architecture and Urban Planning of Sopollitepa Monument //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – С. 49-54.
5. Есбергенов, Б. Е. (2021). Памятник Калиятепы В Городе Джизак Об Изучении Методов Архитектурного Строительства. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY*, 2(9), 69-72.
6. Yerjanovich, Y. B. (2021). Development and Planned Construction of Housing Buildings in Djizak. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 1(2), 109-112.
7. Yerjanovich, Y. B. (2022). Urban Planning of the Medieval Jonbos Fortress. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY*, 2(2), 65-69.
8. Yerjanovich, Y. B. (2022). Ways of Formation of New Architectural Ensembles in the Development of Samarkand City. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY*, 2(1), 97-100.
9. Yerjanovich, Y. B. (2022). The Way of Forming the City of Jizzak in the Middle Ages. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 6, 85-90.
10. Yerjanovich, Y. B. (2022). Construction Work in the City of Jizzakh. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 6, 74-79.
11. Yerjanovich, Y. B. (2022). Cultural Service Institutions in Jizzak. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 6, 68-73.
12. Yerjanovich, Y. B. (2023). Shrines of Zomin and their History. *World of Science: Journal on Modern Research Methodologies*, 2(5), 88-91.
13. Yerjanovich, Y. B. (2023). Application of Nanomaterials in Architecture. *World of Science: Journal on Modern Research Methodologies*, 2(5), 84-87.
14. Yerjanovich, Y. B. (2023). Scientific Research Work of the Zomin in the Historical Fortress of Miq. *World of Science: Journal on Modern Research Methodologies*, 2(5), 92-96.

15. Yerjanovich, Y. B. (2023). Methods of Preservation of Historical and Cultural Heritage Objects in the City of Jizzah. *World of Science: Journal on Modern Research Methodologies*, 2(5), 97-102.
16. Yerjanovich, Y. B. (2023). About Construction Works in Jizzakh during the Years of Independence. *World of Science: Journal on Modern Research Methodologies*, 2(5), 103-108.
17. Yerjanovich, Y. B., & Mamadiyoroglu, A. A. (2021). ABOUT THE URBAN PLANNING PRACTICE OF THE URDA FORTRESS OF ANCIENT JIZZAK. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 1(5), 148-151.
18. Yerjanovich, Y. B., & Mamadiyoroglu, A. A. (2021). Principles of Using Ornamental Plants in the Interior. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 1(2), 79-81.
19. Qudratovich, B. B. (2023). Personnel Issues in the Application of Nanotechnology in Construction and Architecture.
20. Bobobekov, B. K. (2022). Prospective Directions of Tourism Routes in the Development of Pilgrimage Tourism in Jizak Region. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY*, 2(1), 55-59.
21. Bobobekov, B. K. (2023). Application of Nanotechnology in Architecture and Construction. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(3), 92-96.
22. Bobobekov, B. K., & Bobobekov, B. B. (2023). Issues of Architectural and Landscape Organization of Pedestrian Tourist Routes (PTM) in the Historical Cities of Uzbekistan. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(3), 97-101.
23. Abduazizovich, R. L., & Kilichevich, L. D. (2022, November). DEVELOPMENT OF ISLAMIC ARCHITECTURE AND ITS IMPACT ON INDIAN ARCHITECTURE. In *INTERDISCIPLINE INNOVATION AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 1-5).
24. Рахимов, Л. А., & Лукмонов, Д. Қ. (2023). ҚАДИМГИ ҲИНДИСТОН ДАВРИДА САИДЛАР ВА ЛЎДИЛАР АРХИТЕКТУРАСИНИНГ ИЛМИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ. *ARHITEKTURA, MUHANDISLIK VA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR JURNALI*, 2(2), 85-88.
25. Рахимов, Л. А., & Лукмонов, Д. Қ. (2023). ҲИНДИСТОН ЁЗМА МАНБАЛАРИДА АНЪАНАВИЙ ҚИШЛОҚЛАР БУНЁД ЭТИШНИНГ ТАРХИЙ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ. *ARHITEKTURA, MUHANDISLIK VA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR JURNALI*, 2(2), 89-91.
26. Luqmonov, D., & Jurayeva, E. (2023). Muqarnas Decorations: A Masterpiece of Islamic Architecture. *Genius Repository*, 22, 13-18.
27. Qilichevich, L. D. (2023). Analysis of Akbar Agra Fort. *Genius Repository*, 21, 1-5.
28. Sultanova, D. N., & Dusanov, Z. Z. (2020). Самарқанд-рассомлар шаҳри. *Молодой ученый*, (12), 324-332.
29. Султанова, Д. Н. (2018). Традиционность художников Жарских в декорировании многоэтажных домов. *Молодой ученый*, (23), 231-236.
30. Sultanova, D. (2012). Artistic Means of Agitation and Propaganda in Urban and Architectural Space of Modern Uzbekistan. *Young Scientist USA*, 5, 88.
31. Султанова, Д. Н. (2013). Возникновение и взаимосвязь монументальной живописи в традиционной архитектуре Средней Азии. *Молодой ученый*, (12), 710-719.

32. Султонова, Д. Н. (2004). Ўзбекистон меъморчилигида маҳобатли рангтасвирни уйғунлаштириш тамойиллари/номзодлик диссертацияси.
33. Mamadiyor o'g'li, A. A. (2023). Best Indoor Shade Plants for Low-Light Rooms. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(3), 207-212.
34. Abdullayev, A. (2023). Best Indoor Shade Plants for Low-Light Rooms. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(3), 213-218.
35. Mamadiyor o'g'li, A. A. (2023). Biological Characteristics of Herbaceous and Woody Plants in the Interior Environment. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(3), 236-239.
36. Mamadiyor o'g'li, A. A. (2023). Experiences in Organizing Special Corners for Decorative Plants. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(3), 229-232.
37. Mamadiyor o'g'li, A. A. (2023). Indoor Flowers and their Transplantation. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(3), 250-254.
38. Mamadiyor o'g'li, A. A. (2023). Constructive and Technological Features of Using Plants in the Interior Environment. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(4), 321-323.
39. Mamadiyor o'g'li, A. A. (2023). Biological Characteristics of Vegetable and Woody Plants in the Interior Environment. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(4), 308-310.
40. Mamadiyor o'g'li, A. A. (2022). LANDSCAPE PLANTS IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION BUILDINGS. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 9, 80-83.
41. Mamadiyor o'g'li, A. A. (2022). FOREIGN EXPERIENCES OF USING DECORATIVE PLANTS IN THE INTERIORS OF PUBLIC BUILDINGS. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 9, 76-79.
42. Abdullayev, A. (2022). Kindergarten Territory Landscape Design. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY*, 2(2), 5-8.
43. Abdullayev, A. (2022). Formation of Landshut Territories in the Interior. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY*, 2(2), 1-4.
44. Abdullayev, A. (2022). PRINCIPLES OF USE OF WALL PICTURES IN THE INTERIOR OF ARCHITECTURE OF UZBEKISTAN AND HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 9, 141-143.
45. Abdullayev, A. (2022). GEOGRAPHICAL LANDSCAPE CONDITIONS IN THE RESEARCH OF ARCHITECTURAL AND DESIGN SOLUTIONS OF UZBEKISTAN SANATORIUMS. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 9, 136-140.
46. Abdullayev, A. (2023). Best Indoor Shade Plants for Low-Light Rooms. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(3), 213-218.